

**KNOWLEDGE OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN TECHNOLOGY IS THE
DEMAND OF THE TIMES**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10007796>

Summary: the article provides information and recommendations about the necessity of learning foreign languages, the attitude towards the Russian language in the world.

Keywords: world civilization, information and communication, scientific and practical activity, international cooperation, cooperation network, internship, distance learning, modern education.

Today, knowledge of foreign languages is of great importance, so reforming the system of teaching foreign languages, using advanced methods of teaching using modern pedagogic and information-communication technologies in lesson processes is the first urgent issue in education. Especially nowadays, in the process of globalization, which is happening in all fields, it is becoming a vital necessity for our citizens to know foreign languages for business trips abroad, signing all kinds of mutual agreements, going on trips, going to study abroad, and using the Internet service in scientific and practical activities. For this reason, special conditions, opportunities, and privileges are being created for teaching foreign languages in our country, and it has risen to the level of state policy and has become a national interest.

In this regard, the decision "On measures to further improve the system of learning foreign languages" adopted on December 10, 2012 became the theoretical basis. . This decision is a logical continuation of the Law "On Education" and the "National Program of Personnel Training". In this document, serious attention is paid to a number of topical issues such as the fundamental improvement of the system of training foreign language specialists, as well as the creation of conditions and opportunities for their achievements of world civilization, extensive use of world information resources, and the development of international cooperation and communication on the basis of this[1].

The main goal of this decision is to teach foreign languages to the young generation by introducing advanced methods of teaching using modern pedagogical and information technologies, to prepare specialists who can speak these languages freely. At present, a foundation has been created for young

people to widely use the news of world civilization and world information resources, to develop international cooperation and mutual communication.

In our country, with the initiatives of the honorable President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, all conditions are being created for the young generation to learn foreign languages in depth, as well as to provide them with modern knowledge. For this purpose, the most modern education and information technologies are actively involved, and special attention is paid to the quality and competence of personnel being trained in this direction. As a result of the implemented works, the quality of foreign language teaching is improving and its effectiveness is increasing. For example, an agreement on cooperation with the Department of Russian Language and Literature of Fergana State University and the Institute of Russian Language named after A.S. Pushkin in Moscow, Russian Federation was signed on November 30, 2017 in Fergana. In May 2019, an agreement was signed with St. Petersburg State University of the Russian Federation, and in 2021, a similar agreement was signed with Kazan Federal University.

Based on the agreed contract, the "Cooperation Network" of the Institute of Russian Language was opened at the Fergana State University. A.S. Pushkin Institute "Cooperation Network" operates in the field of higher education on a large scale. For example, teaching the Russian language, training of Russian language specialists, advanced training and retraining, internship, student exchange, distance learning, etc.

In the past period, from the Moscow Institute of Russian Language named after A.S. Pushkin to the Department of Russian Language and Literature of Fergana State University, Doctor of Philological Sciences, Professor A.A. Katyshev, E.N. Pavlicheva, E.K. Peterivnyaya, Candidate of Philological Sciences, Associate Professor Bogouddin According to the 28-hour program, the Karadjevs held a seminar, a lecture and a "master class", in which the participating department and university professors were given certificates of advanced training. On December 17-21, 2017, the days of the international expedition "Ambassadors of the Russian language to the world" were held in Fergana. Students, professors and teachers of the department of Russian language and literature, students of Fergana city 6 - general education school took part in it and exchanged experiences. On November 5-9, the senior teacher of the department, N. Sobirov, participated in the World Assembly of Russian language teachers held in Moscow, gave a lecture and brought many methodological manuals for professors and teachers. Associate professor of the department G.N. Davlyatova took part in the Khalyaro scientific-practical

conference called "Elektronnye resursy otkrytogo obrazovaniya po russkomu yazyku: luchshie praktikari" held at the A.S. Pushkin Institute of the Russian Language on December 7-8. brought back educational and methodological recommendations. On March 1-29, the members of the department N. Sobirov and M. Tursunova students have improved their skills in applying new pedagogical technologies to the educational process.

In May 2019, professor G.I. Popova, doctor of philological sciences from St. Petersburg State University of Russia, candidate of pedagogical sciences, associate professor I.N. Erofeeva, head of the department of applied linguistics, doctor of philological sciences, professor L.F. Gerbiklar from Belarus State University visited They regularly hold master classes and master classes for our students and graduate students, young pedagogues. Organizing various

didactic educational events for perfect mastery of foreign languages and creating an environment for language learning and providing them with the necessary programs and materials during the lesson, organizing additional lessons outside of class, writing dictation and narration, writing essays and essays, holding quizzes and discussions, solving tests , learning to write course work, independent work, and graduate qualification work in foreign languages is important for improving students' knowledge [2].

In addition, it is more convenient for students to use display classrooms equipped with computers, which are convenient and easy to learn foreign languages. It is possible to conduct computer lessons on various topics. But they require special training and computer programs. Students develop their knowledge with the help of computer-programmed topics during the lesson. Not just improving. It also improves computer skills. Researcher D. Nurmatova divides teaching foreign languages to students into 3 pure methodological principles:

1. General.
2. Private.
3. Special. The general principles include: the principle of speech orientation of foreign language teaching, the principle of limited and holistic teaching of foreign languages, the principle of giving the main place to exercises, the principle of taking language experience into account.

It is related to specific principles and consists in reflecting methodical phenomena in the narrow sense. Special principles: teaching foreign languages based on speech samples, connecting language exercises with speech practice, interaction of speech activity types, promotion of oral speech, acceleration of the

first stage of approaching natural speech in a foreign language. A special principle includes the teaching of grammatical vocabulary and the use of phonetic writing in teaching [3].

In conclusion, we can say that today, young people who want to find their place in life, to be aware of the achievements of modern science, definitely learn foreign languages as well as their mother tongue, and use all their opportunities to contribute to the development of science and production in our republic. will be needed.

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